

TELEMETRY [101119747]: Trustworthy mEthodologies, open knowLedgE & autoMated tools for sEcurity Testing of IoT software, haRdware & ecosYstems

D5.1 Dissemination & Communication Plan

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Document description	The current document contains the Communication and Dissemination plan of the consortium for the project, with relevant targets identified and the KPIs that need to be achieved. Also, audiences and stakeholders are identified and a roadmap consisting of three phases is provided.

Disclaimer

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Executive Summary

This document is the TELEMETRY deliverable D5.1 “Dissemination and Communication Plan” that includes the actions relevant to Task 5.1 “Dissemination, Communications & Outreach”. This document sets out the dissemination and communication strategy as well as the plan to raise awareness, share knowledge, and attract potential stakeholders in the context of the TELEMETRY project, through various means. These means include the TELEMETRY website, the use of social media, the distribution of communication material, publications in scientific journals, participation in conferences & other relevant events and organisation of workshops and demonstrations with potential end-users. The report provides a comprehensive framework for actions that will support outreach efforts necessary to disseminate and communicate the achievements and benefits of the TELEMETRY project. It provides a focused dissemination & communication approach towards the key target audiences and the best approaches to engage and inform stakeholders to maximise knowledge of TELEMETRY activities.

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List of Terms and Abbreviations

Abbreviation	Definition
ARK	Archival Resource
DOI	Digital Object Identifier
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
PID	Persistent Identifier
Purl	Persistent uniform resource locator
T	Task
URI	Uniform Resource Identifier
WP	Work package
WPs	Work packages

1 Introduction

1.1 Purpose and Scope

This dissemination & communication strategy provides a comprehensive framework for actions that will support outreach efforts necessary to disseminate and communicate the achievements and benefits of the TELEMETRY project. It provides a focused dissemination & communication approach towards the key target audiences and the corresponding channels to reach them most effectively as well as the timing of these activities and the partners responsible for their implementation. As the European Union distinguishes between dissemination and communication, we also support this distinction and provide a detailed definition of the meaning of both dissemination and communication in the context of TELEMETRY. This enables the reader to gain a clear understanding of both the difference and overlap between the two concepts in terms of audiences and channels when combining them into an overall strategy, as presented in the subsequent chapters of this deliverable.

1.1.1 Definition & Scope of Communication within TELEMETRY Project

The European Commission (EC) has defined communication as *"the means of taking strategic and targeted measures for promoting the action itself and its results to a multitude of audiences, including the media and the public, and possibly engaging in a two-way exchange. The purpose is to reach out to society as a whole and specific audiences while demonstrating how EU funding contributes to tackling societal challenges"*.

In light of this definition, communication within the TELEMETRY project will encompass all efforts to inform the audience about the project, its activities, and its results. This includes communication about the project, such as its general description, consortium partners, objectives, approach, and other relevant information. Furthermore, communication will also include disseminating specific project results, facts, and figures, as well as communication about upcoming events and project activities. In short, communication will play a crucial role in raising awareness about TELEMETRY, its goals, and the impact it aims to achieve.

1.1.2 Definition & Scope of Dissemination within TELEMETRY Project

According to the EC, dissemination is the active process of promoting and raising awareness about the results of a project to various stakeholder groups, including research peers, industry and other commercial actors, professional organisations, and policymakers. It involves public disclosure of project results in any medium and enables stakeholders to use the outcomes in their own work.

Within the TELEMETRY project, we interpret dissemination as a process of actively disseminating project results to different stakeholders through various channels. These channels include scientific publications such as conferences and journals, project workshops, webinars, and online repositories of project results and data.

To ensure that our dissemination efforts align with the guidelines set by the EC for Horizon Europe 2021-2027 actions, the consortium follows their guidance on how to communicate and promote the project. We also emphasize the importance of open access to research results and data, in line with the EC's open access policy and open access repository guidelines.

To promote open access to project results, TELEMETRY will publish all public project deliverables, outcomes, and raw research data on the project website, (<https://www.telemetry-project.eu>). Publications in TELEMETRY should be publicly available as a minimum of “Green Open Access” and might be stored at open repositories such as Zenodo (<https://zenodo.org/>), GitHub (<https://github.com/>) and Open Research Europe (<https://open-research-europe.ec.europa.eu/>) to ensure that our scientific publications and research data are freely accessible to all stakeholders.

1.2 Relation to other Work Packages and Deliverables

The activities and the outcome of WP5 “Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach,” and more specifically of Task 5.1 “Dissemination, Communications & Outreach” are highly dependent on receiving inputs from all work packages, tasks, and deliverables of TELEMETRY project. In this deliverable, all project partners have contributed to building the dissemination and communication plan and the results of other WPs will be presented and communicated, via WP5. The most important outcomes of every WP will be presented to a wider audience through the current WP, via dedicated meetings and specific dissemination and communication templates. Finally, every project’s public deliverable will be reaching the ‘outside world’ via the activities of WP5. Therefore, the activities described in this document are in high dependence on the activities of all the WPs and the corresponding Deliverables.

1.3 Methodology and Structure of the Deliverable

This plan is a living document involving all the partners, with regular updates along with the project’s periodic reports. The updated plans will list the dissemination and communication activities implemented and planned. In addition, all final dissemination and communication activities of the project will be reported in deliverable D5.5 “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities (interim version)” in month 18, and in deliverable D5.3 “Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities (final version)” in month 36.

This deliverable is structured as follows for the remaining chapters.

- Chapter 2 presents the dissemination & communication strategy. More specifically, the dissemination and communication objectives of the project are mentioned as well as the dissemination and communication phases to reach the target audience and achieve the strategy’s objectives are defined.
- Chapter 3 analyses the target stakeholders and audiences, addresses the appropriate channels for approaching the target groups, and describes the individual stakeholders to be reached.
- Section 4 provides a detailed description of the dissemination and communication channels/activities.
- Chapter 5 describes the design and establishment of the project’s visual identity.
- Chapter 6 outlines the dissemination and communication time plan of the project.
- Chapter 7 provides a qualitative and quantitative evaluation of the communication and dissemination activities while describing and estimating their impact. An analysis of risks and potential issues related to the communication and dissemination side of the project is also presented.
- Chapter 8 describes the roles and responsibilities of all partners engaged in the dissemination and communication activities.
- Finally, Chapter 9 concludes this deliverable.

2 TELEMETRY Dissemination & Communication Strategy

2.1 Objectives

TELEMETRY will provide trustworthy tools that enable the continuous assessment of heterogeneous, interlinked components & systems that constitute IoT ecosystems (interconnected IoT devices with hardware, software, services and communications infrastructure).

Addressing all aspects of their lifecycle, the TELEMETRY holistic methodology and toolkit incorporates:

- testing for component development
- testing & monitoring for component integration into systems
- testing & monitoring for operation of systems.

TELEMETRY will deliver advances in cybersecurity testing and runtime monitoring through the use of novel machine learning models and algorithms for real-time anomaly detection; dynamic risk assessment to simulate likelihood and severity of threat consequences; reputation management and privacy-preserving data sharing across independent entities (e.g. supply chains), IoT device emulation and analysis environment and lightweight approaches for trusted updates; all of which that promotes a cycle of continuous improvement and assurance across design and runtime phases.

TELEMETRY will leverage 3 exemplary use cases representing diverse, complex IoT ecosystems and IoT supply chains in aerospace, smart manufacturing and telecommunications domains to drive the design and validation of the proposed tools and methodologies. This will lead to significant improvements with respect to accuracy of threat and vulnerability detection, response time and cost of testing and verification of IoT ecosystems.

TELEMETRY will promote open source and knowledge sharing through engagement with relevant communities throughout the project for consultation, dissemination and exploitation of its results.

Towards this end, TELEMETRY central dissemination & communication objectives are to:

- Provide visibility and public awareness of the project by following a strategy targeting the critical actors in the broader European community and national public bodies;
- Publish results in international industrial and academic conferences, workshops and journals to inform the relevant interested third parties (academic/research and private/public organisations) about TELEMETRY;
- Support cluster collaboration to enhance cross-fertilization among projects of the funded under the same Call (HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02).

2.2 Dissemination & Communication Phases for the Project

The dissemination and communication activities of TELEMETRY results will differ in intensity based on the evolution of the project. The dissemination and communication activities will be

carried out in three main phases, spanning throughout the project's duration and extend beyond it, with increasing level of intensity, starting from the creation of general awareness and concluding with attracting potential stakeholders and users of the project results, through events such as trainings, workshops and more. The three phases are presented in Table 1, as follows.

Table 1: Dissemination & Communication Phases

Phase	Objectives	Type of Information	Dissemination & Communication Channels/Activities
Phase I	Inform & Connect: Create awareness about the project.	Approach-oriented content; project presentation; objectives; expected results.	<p>Use traditional & online communication channels (project website, press releases, social media, postings, flyers, newsletters etc.);</p> <p>Open access publications in scientific journals, publications in general printed/online media, participation in events and international conferences to gain insights from and better links to manufacturing and industrial communities;</p> <p>Creation of project video;</p> <p>Organization and participation in clustering activities with other EU projects in order to establish a core cluster, discuss cross-fertilisation and the implementation of joint activities;</p> <p>Industrial partners' network.</p>
Phase II	Demonstrate & Contribute: Promote the novel services & show cases; Engage target users & early adopters in the project activities.	Result-oriented content; project intermediate results.	<p>Project website & Social Media;</p> <p>Press releases, newsletters, flyers;</p> <p>Open access publications in scientific journals, publications in general printed/online media, participation in events and international conferences;</p> <p>Further and continuous action will be taken in Clustering</p>

			<p>activities exploiting synergies between the projects and increasing their impact. Common areas of collaboration will be agreed, and actions will be taken in identified areas which address similar technology needs;</p> <p>Synergies with EU Initiatives as well as with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms; Disseminate the TELEMETRY outcomes to student conferences.</p>
Phase III	Share & Convince: Leverage the exploitation of the outcomes.	Result-oriented content; project final results and lessons learnt.	<p>Project website & Social Media;</p> <p>Press releases, newsletters;</p> <p>Open access publications in scientific journals, publications in general</p>

The timing of the phases has been adjusted based on the ongoing work in the project relating to what has already been accomplished and what is yet to come. This means that phases are overlapping and partially parallel as shown in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Dissemination and Communication Phases within the Project Time plan

2.2.1 Phase I: Inform & Connect (M1-M36)

In this early phase of the project there are two main goals for the communication and dissemination activities. One is to concentrate on making the project known among its different target audiences. The other is to connect audiences around the world for input and collaboration.

Making the project known among the target audiences is key to creating awareness for the project, getting people on board and interest them in the work. Communicating the project objectives, concepts, specifications as well as research findings will be key tasks to achieve this.

This can best be done through channels like the project website, press releases, newsletters and events participation. But also, through the use of multiple social networks like X and LinkedIn, through which we will be able to spread information about the project and connect to experts and interested individuals and groups.

The “Inform & Connect” phase extends over the whole project’s lifetime. Creating a network of high influencers in the areas of the project will be a main goal of this phase, but also raising general awareness of the project, proclamation of project goals, concepts and research findings among researchers and target users.

2.2.2 Phase II: Demonstrate & Contribute (M18-M36)

The second communication and dissemination phase is all about demonstrating progress of the project and getting people to contribute to the work. This involves future users of the TELEMETRY framework & tools, **Component Developers (CDs)**, **System Integrators (SIs)** and **System Operators (SOs)**, as well as scientific experts from other (EU / research) projects for collaboration. Building on a successful first phase of communication, this can best be achieved by using the established connections and networks.

Presenting early achievements of the project will work as calls-to-action, asking audiences for feedback and ideas, but also showing them how the project progresses. It is very important to have first components or examples to share with the audience. These should be accompanied by explanations from technical partners describing the current state of technical developments and future steps.

To successfully implement this phase, it is necessary to have adequate feedback channels in place, through which users can reply. Social media channels are a great way for this, as well as a contact form on the website and a project-email should be established for this.

First steps of the “Demonstrate & Contribute” phase will be taken already during the first year (e.g. awareness of the project to other projects) since its concepts do overlap with the “Inform & Connect” phase. The first real activity, however, will not start until the first results are available and the technical direction of the project is clear. These activities will continue until the end of the project. The dissemination efforts will be focused on providing use case results, samples and feedback channels.

2.2.3 Phase III: Share & Convince (M30-M36)

The third phase of the dissemination and communication strategy is expected to take place within the third year of the project. The focus in this phase will be on sharing achieved results and on convincing end users to test and start using the TELEMETRY framework & tools. The main dissemination activity in this phase will have two main focuses.

- User focus: Showcasing the TELEMETRY solution and engaging with early users to get feedback on the outcomes of the TELEMETRY project.
- Technical focus: Sharing project results and testing the technical TELEMETRY framework & tools, showcasing tools and methodologies developed in terms of the project and cutting-edge technologies used in this development, etc.

These activities take place at various events, conferences, or workshops. They are also provided through marketing material on the website and through the different established social media channels (where applicable).

The success of these dissemination efforts depends on stable results of the project.

2.2.4 Final integration towards end of project and beyond

Before completely wrapping up the project, it will be crucial to evaluate the connections made during the project's duration in order to get beyond the mere project status. With a successful TELEMETRY framework & tools at hand, gaining further collaborators and even a continuation of the development of the TELEMETRY framework & tools is a lot easier. Communication will at this point aim at presenting the successful results of the consortium's work as well as at winning stakeholders who see potential in the project's results.

Of course, in order to share a convincing message, it is absolutely crucial to have a working prototype/ integration of the TELEMETRY framework & tools that can be presented to possible collaborators and interested groups. Using the established channels, the progress and success of the project will be communicated, aiming at a broad audience as well as at particular interest groups. One central part of this will be the website and the connected social media channels. Another one should be direct contacts through conferences, workshops and demonstrations with potential end-users including presentations of the results.

All these activities are already part of phase 3, only gaining a special focus once the official project ends and the final evaluation is near. Ideally the communication of the project and its results continues beyond the official end, which depends very much on the results and their tangibility and usability.

3 Target Audience

3.1 Defining the audience for TELEMETRY

TELEMETRY specifically targets **Component Developers (CDs), System Integrators (SIs) and System Operators (SOs)**, as these roles correspond to the lifecycle of components and systems.

According to credible statistics (as mentioned in the Grant Agreement), there are *over 6 million CDs - software developers in Europe and there are around 5600 companies developing hardware in the EU. In terms of SIs, the market size is €207bn per annum. Regarding SOs, specifically for these sectors, in Europe there are 1418 aerospace companies, approximately 15000 large manufacturing companies and 150+ telecom Operators.*

Other direct TELEMETRY beneficiaries include **cybersecurity researchers** and scientific **community & the academia**, who will be benefitted by TELEMETRY’s papers and datasets.

An indirect beneficiary of TELEMETRY is **policymakers and regulators**, which TELEMETRY will support via methodologies to achieve certification to specific standards for the project’s use cases and common standards within the EUCC (Standard Development Organizations in EU: ETSI, CEN, CENELEC). Also, the **scientific community & the academia**, are stakeholders who will benefit from research conducted within TELEMETRY’s and relevant scientific results such as papers and datasets.

An indirect beneficiary of TELEMETRY is **policymakers and regulators**, which TELEMETRY will support via methodologies to achieve certification to specific standards for the project’s use cases and common standards within the EUCC. (Standard Development Organizations in EU: ETSI, CEN, CENELEC).

Finally, the **general public** benefits indirectly from more secure software and devices inside and outside their homes.

Table 2: Approaching Target Groups

Target Group	Channel/Activity	Main direction for messages
Component Developers (CDs), System Integrators	Project website	How the outcomes of the project will help them to
	Social Media	
	Events and presentations	
	Flyers and newsletters	
	International conferences and stands	
	Synergies with national or regional initiatives,	

<p>(Sis) and System Operators (Sos)</p>	<p>funding programs and platforms</p> <p>Training material and demos</p> <p>Workshops and demonstrations</p> <p>Articles in printed/online media</p> <p>Press releases</p> <p>Video</p> <p>Partners' networks</p>	<p>identify solutions for day-to-day operations;</p> <p>What breakthroughs should their company benefit from;</p>
<p>Scientific Community (Incl. EU initiatives and associations)</p>	<p>Project website</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Flyers and newsletters</p> <p>International conferences and stands</p> <p>Open access publications in Scientific Journals</p> <p>Clustering (Liaison)</p> <p>Activities with other EU projects</p> <p>Synergies with EU Initiatives</p> <p>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</p> <p>Workshops and demonstrations</p>	<p>What are the research, technological and industrial breakthroughs of the project; What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How these can be used and further exploited;</p> <p>Open research questions and steps ahead;</p> <p>Open access of project results for scientific purposes.</p>
<p>Academia & Cybersecurity research</p>	<p>Project website</p> <p>Social Media</p> <p>Flyers and newsletters</p> <p>International conferences and stands</p> <p>Open access publications in Scientific Journals</p> <p>Clustering (Liaison)</p> <p>Activities with other EU projects</p>	<p>What are the research, technological and industrial breakthroughs of the project; What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How these can be used and further exploited;</p> <p>Open research questions and steps ahead;</p>

	<p>Synergies with EU Initiatives</p> <p>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</p> <p>Workshops and demonstrations</p>	<p>Open access of project results for academic purposes.</p>
<p>General public</p>	<p>Project website</p> <p>Social Media</p>	<p>What are the research, technological and industrial breakthroughs of the project; What is the innovation of the project;</p> <p>How these tools can be used and further exploited;</p>

3.2 Reaching Target Audiences (ALL PARTNERS)

An initial list of organizations, associations, agencies, which constitute key stakeholders for TELEMETRY is provided in Table 3, below. This list will be expanded during the project period.

Table 3: Indicative Target Audiences

Name	Short Description	Type	Website
ENISA	European Union Agency for Cybersecurity	Cybersecurity Agency	https://www.enisa.europa.eu/
GSMA	GSM Association	Standardization organization	https://www.gsma.com/
ECSO	European Cyber Security Organisation	Policymaker	https://ecs-org.eu/
ETSI	European Telecommunications Standards Institute	SDO	https://www.etsi.org/
CEN/CENELEC	European Committee for Standardization	SDO	https://www.cencenelec.eu/
3GPP	3rd Generation Partnership Project	Standardization organization	https://www.3gpp.org/
W4C	Non-profit European private foundation	Women4Cyber Italia	https://women4cyber.it/
MTU	Ministry of Infrastructure	Ministry of Ukraine	https://mtu.gov.ua/
BDVA	Big Data Value Association	Association	https://bdva.eu/
NESSI	Association for Software, Data and Digital Services	Association	https://nessi.eu/

MDT	Ministry of Digital Transformation	Ministry of Ukraine	https://mdt.gov.tt/
USPP	Ukrainian League of Industrialists And Entrepreneurs	Industry Association	https://uspp.ua/

4 Dissemination and Communication Activities

The TELEMETRY consortium makes use of a variety of dissemination and communication channels/activities. Table 4 below outlines the dissemination and communication channels/activities that are deployed by the TELEMETRY consortium and shows how these help increase the impact of the project.

Table 4: Dissemination-Communication Channels/Activities

Channel/Activity	Description	Benefit of the Channel/Activity
Website	<p>Establish online presence – a website where the interested parties can read about the project progress and findings;</p> <p>Create an online repository on the website for anyone to download project findings and public deliverables.</p>	<p>The project website is a key instrument for enhancing the visibility of the project; The website clearly refers visitors to the TELEMETRY vision and educates them about the project concept; All project findings are published on the website to allow anyone interested in the subject to follow the progress of the project.</p>
Social media	<p>Create an X account and a LinkedIn Page for sharing project news, events, resources, demonstrations, publications and reach people that are interested in the outcomes of the project; Use consortium social networking contacts (X, LinkedIn) to reach out to a wide range of communities.</p>	<p>Social media are fast, low-cost channels of reaching interested groups and communities that are normally not present at any events, conferences.</p>
Partners' networks	<p>Disseminate the results to partner networks</p>	<p>Sharing of the project results with the partners' networks will increase the visibility of the project results highlighting the project's innovations and their potential applications.</p>
Flyers	<p>Create flyers with key project public information to be distributed at events and downloaded from the TELEMETRY website.</p>	<p>Project flyers distributed at various events, conferences, workshops etc. gain the project visibility with the general public.</p>
Newsletters	<p>Distribute online Newsletters to all stakeholders to inform them about project progress and developments.</p>	<p>Project newsletters show the progress of the project to all stakeholders and keep their interest high.</p>

<p>International conferences and stands</p>	<p>Submission of Abstracts and Full papers relevant to the scientific progress of the project (for peer-reviewed academic conferences). Stands and exhibitions in industrial conferences.</p>	<p>Peer reviewed academic conferences will provide an academic dissemination of the project outcomes to the specific audience and enable cross validation of the outcomes. For conferences focused on security issues the benefits include a wide dissemination of the outputs of the project and further collaboration and lead generation for potential customers.</p>
<p>Open access publications in Scientific Journals</p>	<p>Submission of full papers relevant to the scientific progress of the project (for peer-reviewed scientific journals). Publishing Open Access means making publications available free of charges, therefore available online for all the persons interested in it.</p>	<p>Peer reviewed scientific journals will provide an academic dissemination of the project outcomes to the specific audience and enable cross validation of the outcomes. The benefit of Open Access publications in Scientific Journals is the sharing of results connected with the TELEMETRY project, favoring the science progress through accessible literature to every interested stakeholder</p>
<p>Synergies with EU initiatives</p>	<p>Finding, establishing, and fostering collaborations and synergies with relevant European Union (EU) initiatives that align with the goals and objectives of the project, and maintaining active relationship by involving other projects into TELEMETRY activities.</p>	<p>Finding relevant synergies will allow to leverage existing resources, knowledge, and networks to enhance its impact and contribute to the broader EU framework.</p>
<p>Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms</p>	<p>New partnerships with relevant national or regional initiatives, funding programs, and platforms that might develop into new funding opportunities, joint projects, and knowledge exchange activities.</p>	<p>Finding relevant synergies will allow to leverage local resources, expertise, and funding opportunities to enhance the project's impact and facilitate knowledge exchange.</p>
<p>Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects</p>	<p>The objective of clustering activities is to increase the technical and social impact of the TELEMETRY results on</p>	<p>The clustering activities with other EU projects can allow the advancing of cooperation and exchanging</p>

	European level; this will be possible thanks to the collaboration and technical discussions with other EU projects.	of knowledge contributing to the success and the positive impact of the involved projects.
Training-demos	To develop and make available online training materials and specific demos related to the TELEMETRY project.	Training-demos will provide valuable resources to interested parties, including stakeholders, professionals, researchers, and the broader community, to enhance their understanding and practical knowledge of the project's concepts, technologies, and lessons learned. Also, wider teams of Pilot Users' personnel will be trained on using developed tools and to apply developed methodologies
Workshops and demonstrations	The showcase of technologies and solutions developed by the project partners in the context of TELEMETRY. The workshops will be hosted by technological project partners.	The workshops and demonstrations will provide hands-on experiences and practical insights to industry partners, stakeholders, and interested parties, highlighting the project's innovations and their potential applications.
Articles in printed/online media (not scientific)	Articles (and white papers) in industrial magazines relevant to the technologies of the project	A focused communication of the project outputs for specific target audiences that are subscribed to the various outlets.
Student conferences	Paper abstracts, Full papers, panels, workshops with material relevant to the project outcomes	A wide dissemination to undergraduate and postgraduate students in disciplines relevant to TELEMETRY.
Press Releases	Publish Press releases to highlight project results in English at European/International level.	Press releases can target specific stakeholders depending on the channel where press release is published and can communicate in a regular basis the newest achievements of the project and keep the audiences up to date.
Videos	Project videos showcasing the project challenges and	Promotional videos on TELEMETRY concept and

	objectives in a non-technical and self-explicative way as possible to reach the widest audience.	results will help make the results more obvious, thus appealing to a more generic non-technical audience. Videos are a powerful tool for attracting key stakeholders.
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The rest of this chapter describes in more detail each dissemination and communication channel/activity.

4.1 Project Website

Objective	To spread information about the project's activities and results a dedicated project website has been created (https://www.telemetry-project.eu). It will feature links to the social networking sites that the project is utilizing. The project website will also serve as a repository to store the project-produced content as well as public deliverables of the project.
Content and Messages	Project's objectives, results, impact, partner information, resources (material, public deliverables, publications), and a blog with news and events.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Main project documentation and material; medium-level detail
Information Provider	All Partners for the dissemination activities that undertake in the framework of the project
Communication Methods	Communication Material, Newsletters
Activities	Gathering documentation, editing, and regularly publishing content and news on the website
Schedule	Key revisions every six months updating throughout the project's duration (news and events updated on an ad-hoc basis)
Monitoring	ATC is responsible for monitoring volume of traffic on the site and providing statistics via Google Analytics.
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for building, hosting and maintaining the project website.

4.2 Social Media

4.2.1 X (former Twitter)

Objective	The TELEMETRY X account will be used to promote the project news and related activities as well as reach a wide range of communities.
Content and Messages	Project news, events, resources, collaborations, demonstrations, publications as well as reposting the relevant social media messages.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	All actual information promoting TELEMETRY findings and related information.
Information Provider	All Partners
Communication Methods	Internet
Activities	Encouraging new users to join, regularly adding new posts and responding to comments.
Schedule	Updated on an ad-hoc basis throughout the project.
Monitoring	ATC is monitoring the account
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for creating/operating the account. Each partner is responsible to send news to be added on X.

4.2.2 LinkedIn

Objective	The TELEMETRY LinkedIn page will be used to announce the project's achievements to other professionals from relevant fields of action, to raise questions and obtain feedback that can contribute to the project's development. Also announce events and gather interest from other people that join our community.
Content and Messages	Project news, events, resources, collaborations, demonstrations, publications as well as reposting the relevant social media messages
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	All actual information promoting TELEMETRY findings and related information.
Information Provider	All Partners

Communication Methods	Internet
Activities	Encouraging new users to join, regularly adding new posts and responding to others' comments
Schedule	Weekly, or as we have content to add
Monitoring	ATC is monitoring the page at a minimum twice a week.
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for creating/operating the page. Each partner is responsible to send news to be added on LinkedIn.

4.3 Partners' Networks

Objective	Using networks to disseminate TELEMETRY is a strategic approach to connect with a larger audience, foster collaboration, build a community, and ensure the project's success and sustainability.
Content and Messages	Project Overview, Key Messages, Feedback Mechanism, Compliance and Ethics
Target Audience	Partners of the projects, Clients, Business Units, Policy Makers, EU Associations and SDO
Information Required	Description of all use cases as finalized within the project, along with the development carried out during the project by partners working on each use case including partner contributions.
Information Provider	All partners
Communication Methods	Blogs and Articles, Webinars and Online Events, Podcasts, In-Person Events and Conferences
Activities	Preparation of papers and presentations, Social media posts, contribution to workshops and meetings
Schedule	To be reviewed during project meetings
Monitoring	MTU, I4RI, SINTEF, UoS, NOKIA
Responsible Partner	I4RI

4.4 Flyers

Objective	Create a concise downloadable and printable communication material to generate maximum awareness of the project objectives and planned outcomes. The flyers should be distributed at all dissemination events, conferences, and workshops.
Content and Messages	Project's background; invitation for the Stakeholders to visit the website and join TELEMETRY on social media.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objective, approach and impact, Project's main outcomes, etc.
Information Provider	ATC based on partners' contribution
Communication Methods	Written communication, face-to-face distribution, internet
Activities	Writing content, designing, and printing the document
Schedule	The first flyer will be published in M8. An updated second version will be published in the second half of the project.
Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for content creation based on partners' contribution. ATC is responsible for the design.

4.5 Newsletters

Objective	To inform the audience of the latest news or updates about TELEMETRY achievements, and to inform the stakeholders on the project's scope.
Content and Messages	Key project objectives, project's main results, dissemination activities, and events. The content adheres to the TELEMETRY branding.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objective, approach and impact, Project's main outcomes, dissemination events and conferences attended or organised by TELEMETRY, highlighted relevant news/events/conferences etc.

Information Provider	All partners
Communication Methods	Project's digital channels, list of subscribers.
Activities	Writing content, designing, editing and publishing the newsletters on TELEMETRY website, promoting the newsletters on social media
Schedule	Five newsletters will be published during the project's duration (M9, M16, M24, M30, M36).
Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	ATC is responsible for content creation based on partners' contribution. ATC is responsible for the design.

4.6 International Conferences and Stands

Objective	Disseminate the results of TELEMETRY (scientific and technical) developed in the course of the project to respective audiences. Additionally, to create lead prospects for further exploitation of the Key exploitable outcomes.
Content and Messages	Academic: Results relevant to scientific progress beyond state of art, Impact of solution, Evaluation outcomes. Message: Prove the scientific impact of the developed solution Business: Developed system. Message: Prove the business impact upon introduction of the TELEMETRY framework and tools in the day-to-day operations.
Target Audience	Academic: Academic stakeholders in the different disciplines relevant to TELEMETRY and respective publications. Business: Component Developers (CDs), System Integrators (SIs) and System Operators (SOs), Standardization bodies, Policy makers
Information Required	Academic: Scientific output during the course project Business: Detailed description of the system and its impact, potential buyers
Information Provider	All partners
Communication Methods	Academic: Abstracts/Full Papers in international conferences, Panels, Presentations, Physical, Virtual and Hybrid presence Business: Workshops, Stands in related conferences, Banners, leaflets, Physical, Virtual and Hybrid presence
Activities	Preparation of papers, presentations, complementary communication material

Schedule	During the project development, starting 2024
Monitoring	Academic: MTU, SINTEF, UoS Business: I4RI
Responsible Partner	MTU

4.6.1 Indicative list of international conferences

Table 5 below summarizes the main international events and conferences dealing with topics that are relevant to the TELEMETRY project. The events list will be continuously updated by the partners and each event will be analysed for impact potential before deciding whether TELEMETRY should be represented.

Table 5: Indicative Dissemination events and conferences

Event Name	Date	City, Country	Target Audience
International Conference on Computational Linguistics and Intelligent Systems (CoLInS).	April 2025, 2026	Kharkiv-Lviv, Ukraine	Academic
Information technology and implementation	November 2024, 2025, 2026	Kyiv, Ukraine	Academic
Cyber Science	June 2024	Edinburgh, UK	Academic
IEEE Secure Development Conference	October 2024	Pittsburgh, PA, USA	Academic
Annual Computer Security Applications Conference	December 2024	Waikiki, Hawaii, USA	Academic
ESORICS	September 2024	Bydgoszcz, Poland	Academic
ARES Conference	August 2024	Vienna, Austria	Academic
Nordsec		Karlstad, Sweden	Academic
IoT BDS	April 2024	Angers, France	Academic
WISec	May 2024	Seoul, Korea	Academic

4.7 Open Access Publications in Scientific Journals

Objective	Disseminate TELEMETRY ideas and results, reputation enhancement for academic partners from publication
Content and Messages	Depends on publication idea
Target Audience	Most likely academic community in cybersecurity, IoT providers and domain sectors

Information Required	Idea, contribution, publication target (journal), leader partner, contributor partners
Information Provider	Project partners
Communication Methods	Documents
Activities	Maintain a tracking list of publication ideas and progress on publications at project level and to identify relevant partners and to set actions on them for progressing the publication ideas.
Schedule	Key revisions at the end of each year updating the number of scientific papers achieved from the project partners in journal and conferences, and verification of the open access.
Monitoring	Revisit publication tracking document at each project meeting – update progress on planned publications, seek new ideas and leaders for publications
Responsible Partner	All partners, predominantly academic partners.

4.7.1 Indicative list of International Scientific Journals

An initial list has been made for Scientific Journals, partners will focus on, has been made and initial expression of interest has been made, from partners to participate in some publications, which is summed up in Table 6 below.

Table 6: Indicative Scientific Journals

Scientific Journal	Link (publisher)	Field	Partner(s) Involved
Computers and Security	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/computers-and-security		UoS
System research and information technologies	http://journal.iasa.kpi.ua/		
Problems of Control and Informatics	https://www.begellhouse.com/journals/automation-and-information-sciences.html		
Mathematical Modeling and Computing	https://science.lpnu.ua/mmc		
International Scientific Technical	https://jais.net.ua	the problem of automatic	

Journal "Problems of Control and Informatics"		control and informatics	
Theoretical and Applied Cybersecurity	tacs.ipt.kpi.ua	problems related to the creation of methods and means of information protection	
International Journal of Information Security	https://link.springer.com/journal/10207/updates/17273774	Information security in the broad sense	
International Journal of Critical Infrastructure Protection	https://www.sciencedirect.com/journal/international-journal-of-critical-infrastructure-protection	Critical infrastructure protection	
Journal of Cybersecurity and Privacy	https://www.mdpi.com/journal/jcp	Cybersecurity and privacy	

4.8 Synergies with EU Initiatives

Objective	The results of the project can be relevant for the upcoming Cyber Resilience Act (CRA). The CRA aims to have more secure hardware and software products in the EU market.
Content and Messages	Testing tools and methodologies developed by TELEMETRY, partner information, resources (material, public deliverables, publications).
Target Audience	EU COM, EU SDO (ETSI, CEN/CENELEC), ECSO, EU digital industry representatives/associations, consumers
Information Required	Main project documentation and material; medium-level detail
Information Provider	All Partners for the dissemination activities that undertake in the framework of the project
Communication Methods	Participation to dedicated events, blogs, articles
Activities	Monitoring the evolution of the CRA related standards, evaluating possible contributions to dedicated events and journals

Schedule	Regularly. During the development of the project activities (e.g. plenary meetings, technical reviews).
Monitoring	Plenary meetings
Responsible Partner	ENG

4.8.1 Indicative list of EU Initiatives for potential Synergies

Table 7: EU initiatives for potential synergies with TELEMETRY

National or Regional Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
ECISO (cybersecurity)	ECISO WGs are defining cyber security EU R&I roadmap and vision to strengthen and build a resilient EU ecosystem	TIM
BDVA (big data)		Nokia, SINTEF, UoS, ATC
ENISA (cybersecurity)	EU5G and other certification schemas for the security certification	TIM
ETSI (TC Cyber)	ETSI TC CYBER defines requirements and security testing for IoT and other network devices (e.g. routers)	Nokia, SINTEF, UoS
NESSI		Nokia, MTU, UoS, SINTEF, ATC

4.9 Synergies with national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms

Objective	The objective of this activity is to establish and foster collaborations and synergies with relevant European Union (EU) initiatives that align with the goals and objectives of the project. By doing so, the project aims to leverage existing resources, knowledge, and networks to enhance its impact and contribute to the broader EU framework.
Content and Messages	The content and messages for this activity will focus on highlighting the similarities, complementarities, and potential collaborative opportunities between the TELEMETRY project and other EU initiatives. The messages should emphasize the potential benefits of collaboration, such as knowledge exchange, increased visibility, and shared resources.

Target Audience	The primary target audience for this activity includes relevant EU initiatives, research organizations, industry associations, and key stakeholders involved in related fields. These entities should be interested in exploring synergies and collaborative opportunities to advance the objectives of their respective initiatives.
Information Required	To effectively engage with EU initiatives, it is necessary to gather information about their objectives, ongoing projects, key contacts, and areas of expertise. Additionally, understanding the project's own goals, expertise.
Information Provider	The information required for this activity can be obtained through desk research, online platforms, EU databases, and official websites of relevant EU initiatives, also through partners who are involved into other EU projects.
Communication Methods	Communication methods may include email exchanges, participation in relevant conferences, workshops, and seminars, as well as arranging one-on-one meetings with representatives of the targeted EU initiatives
Activities	Initiating contact with the identified EU initiatives through emails or formal introduction letters. Participating in conferences, workshops, and events where the targeted EU initiatives are present to establish direct communication.
Schedule	The schedule for this activity may vary depending on the availability of relevant conferences and events, as well as the responsiveness of the targeted EU initiatives
Monitoring	Keeping a record of the engagements made, meetings held, and potential collaboration opportunities identified will help evaluate the effectiveness of this activity and inform future strategies.
Responsible Partner	I4RI Also, all partners must be engaged in finding the EU initiatives and establishing contacts in synergy with I4RI

4.9.1 Indicative list of National or Regional Initiatives for potential synergies

Table 8: National or Regional Initiatives for potential synergies with TELEMETRY

National or Regional Initiative	Proposed synergy	Partner(s) Involved
Networked European Software and Services Initiative (NESSI) http://www.nessi-europe.com	Members of Steering Committee	UoS, I4RI, ATC, SINTEF, ENG, NOKIA
UK National Cyber Security Centre	UoS hosts GCHQ Academic Centre of	UoS

(NCSC) https://www.ncsc.gov.uk/	excellence for CyberSec research and UoS CyberSec Academy. Both are directly linked to industry, the cybersec community and NCSC	
AIOTI - https://aioti.eu/	Member	I4RI, SINTEF
ECISO European Cyber Security Organization https://www.ecs-org.eu/	Members. ENG is co-leading SWG6.2 - Cybersecurity for Verticals	SINTEF, TIM, ENG, MTU, NOKIA
Big Data Value Association (BDVA) www.bdva.eu	Board of Directors	ATC, SINTEF, NOKIA, ENG
IIoTSBOM - Security and Software Bill of Materials for IoT https://www.iiotsbom.com/	Partner	KUL
Industrial IoT Consortium	Member, Trustworthiness Working Group	MTU
National Standards Authority of Ireland (NSAI)	Representative on mirror committees, national representative with ISO.	MTU
Cyber Ireland	MTU host cluster for cyber security in Ireland linking industry, academia and public bodies	MTU
ENISA European Union Agency for Cybersecurity	NOKIA and TIM participate in the ENISA AHWG (ad Hoc Working Groups) on 5G (NOKIA, TIM) and eSIM certification (TIM).	TIM, NOKIA
ETSI (European Telecommunications Standards Institute)	Member	TIM, NOKIA
GSMA (Global System for Mobile communications Association)	Member	TIM, NOKIA
3GPP (3rd Generation Partnership Project)	Member	TIM, NOKIA
European Organization for Security	Member	ENG
Computer Emergency Response Team of Ukraine - https://cert.gov.ua/	Potential partner	WRCVE

Scientific Cyber Security Association of Ukraine - https://scsa.org.ua/	Potential partner	WRCVE
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4.10 Clustering (Liaison) Activities with other EU projects

Objective	The objective of clustering activities is to increase the technical and social impact of the TELEMETRY results on European level; this will be possible thanks to the collaboration and technical discussions with other EU projects.
Content and Messages	Project's background, progress and news, value of networks for capacity building
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Information related to the other EU projects involved in the clustering activities.
Information Provider	Stakeholders of other EU projects identified by the partners of TELEMETRY project
Communication Methods	TELEMETRY website; common workshop
Activities	Gathering documentation and information to keep trace of the clustering activities performed in the TELEMETRY project by all partners.
Schedule	Key revisions every six months and also according to the collaborative schedule to be created with the rest of Cluster members, updating the collaboration activities along the project.
Monitoring	I4RI is responsible for monitoring the clustering and connection activities with other EU projects.
Responsible Partner	I4RI

4.10.1 Indicative list of other EU projects for potential synergies

Table 9 presents the list of the Horizon Europe projects funded under the same topic (HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02) that TELEMETRY will seek to establish communication with, or collaboration is envisioned.

Table 9: Horizon Europe projects funded under the same topic

Project name	Acronym	Number
Revolutionised Enhanced Supply Chain Automation with Limited Threats Exposure	RESCALE	101120962
Cybersecurity for AI-Augmented Systems	Sec4AI4Sec	101120393
Secure-by-Design IOT Operation with Supply Chain Control	DOSS	101120270

Also, the table below summarizes Horizon Europe 2021-2027 projects where some TELEMETRY partners also participate, thus they can profit from the common networks and share activities, to reach a broader audience.

This is further enhanced by the fact that the projects below are also engaged in the field of Security and handling datasets with sensitive data, therefore common activities can be organized regarding communication and dissemination.

Table 10: Horizon Europe Projects related to TELEMETRY

Horizon Europe Project	Expected areas of collaboration
NEMECYS	Contributing to the project, joint dissemination events
SYNTHEMA	Contributing to the project, joint dissemination events

4.11 Training-demos

Objective	To train technicians, labs and other technical staff on how to set up and use new tools and methodology developed in TELEMETRY.
Content and Messages	The message to be conveyed to any concerned audience is the innovation potential and the value added by the research in the TELEMETRY project
Target Audience	Internal personnel involved in security testing activities
Information Required	Detailed documentation about the developed tools and methodologies, explanatory use cases.
Information Provider	Each use-case and tool owner

Communication Methods	Written report of the training events in blogs, mailing-list, internal press-releases
Activities	Demo sessions and training courses
Schedule	As far as the results of the project, they are expected to be ready to be used in a real environment, presumably toward the end of the project timeline.
Monitoring	Plenary meetings
Responsible Partner	TIM, NOKIA, ANTONOV

4.12 Workshops and demonstrations

Objective	Demonstrates the effectiveness of the results achieved during the project activities
Content and Messages	The message to be conveyed to any concerned audience is the innovation potential and the value added by the research in the TELEMETRY project
Target Audience	Project reviewers and PO, scientific community, digital industry
Information Required	Information on the addressed use cases and their applicability, value add and maintainability. Detailed documentation about the developed tools and methodologies, explanatory use cases.
Information Provider	Each use-case and tool owner
Communication Methods	Demo events, conferences, posters
Activities	Presentations, workshops, demo sessions and training courses
Schedule	At least two demonstrations, during the technical review of the project
Monitoring	Plenary meetings
Responsible Partner	Use cases and tool owners, WP leaders

4.13 Student conferences

Objective	To disseminate the TELEMETRY outcomes to current students and prospective professionals in the field.
Content and Messages	TELEMETRY can present progress in various fields which will be common practice in the IoT of the future and as such early exposure to future professionals is proposed
Target Audience	Students at undergraduate levels, Students at post-graduate levels
Information Required	Scientific and technical outputs of TELEMETRY in the form of Abstracts and full papers
Information Provider	All partners providing tangible results of their project activities.
Communication Methods	Through the organization bodies of each conference and also TELEMETRY website, TELEMETRY social media.
Activities	Present ongoing research, conduct panels. (E.g. at the International Scientific and Practical Conference of Students and Young Scientists «Information Technologies: Theory and Practice», 2025, 2026)
Schedule	Annual
Monitoring	WRCVE, MTU
Responsible Partner	WRCVE

4.14 Press Releases

Objective	To raise awareness within the widest audience about the project
Content and Messages	Brief summary of the project, the challenges it addresses, its main objectives and partners involved
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objectives, approach and impact, as well as all project partners' names

Information Provider	ATC -to be revised by all partners
Communication Methods	Internet, TELEMETRY website, partners' contacts and network
Activities	Writing content, designing, editing the press releases in English language. Replication of press releases in languages of the consortium countries by all partners at regional/national level, in order to leverage project coverage by reaching out to non-English speaking audiences. Publishing of the press releases on TELEMETRY website. Promoting/emailing press releases on partners' networks.
Schedule	Three times during the project period: after project start to raise awareness within the widest audience about the project; at project midterm to inform on first achievements and tangible benefits; and at project end or shortly after it to promote project results.
Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	ATC. All partners to translate the Press releases to local languages, so as to replicate the activity to regional/national level.

4.15 Videos

Objective	To showcase the project concept and results.
Content and Messages	Promotional videos on TELEMETRY concept, objectives and results.
Target Audience	All Stakeholders
Information Required	Project's concept, objectives, approach and main outcomes.
Information Provider	ATC with contribution from partners
Communication Methods	Project's digital channels
Activities	Writing script, editing and production, publishing the video on the website and promoting the video on social media. Showcasing the video in different project presentations and events.
Schedule	Between M12-M18 of the project.

Monitoring	ATC
Responsible Partner	All partners as content providers, ATC is responsible for final scripting and rendering.

5 Visual Identity

Within the first months of the project, and to pursue the establishment of a strong visual identity that will help TELEMETRY to achieve its potential impact, the project identity kit is being produced, including the project branding and templates for internal and external materials.

5.1 Logo

The logo has been created to sign off the project's identity, and to be applied on all communication collaterals and outlets (see Figure 2) including the website, the project's templates, its social media profiles, and more. It will also be available for downloading on the project's website.

Figure 2: TELEMETRY logo – basic version

An alternative colour variation of the logo, applicable to a dark background, has also been created. (see Figure 3)

Figure 3: TELEMETRY logo – alternative version

5.2 Colour palette

TELEMETRY uses the following colour palette as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 4: TELEMETRY colour palette

5.3 Display of EU funding information

All TELEMETRY communication or dissemination materials must display the EU funding information, including the EU emblem and the funding statement (as shown in Figure 5 below).

Figure 5: EU emblem and funding statement

Moreover, all materials produced must indicate the following disclaimer:

“This project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101119747. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.”

5.4 Brand guide

A complete TELEMETRY brand guide featuring the logo and its use, the colour scheme, typography, imagery, brand elements etc. has been shared with all consortium partners. It should be followed across all dissemination and communication activities.

5.5 Document templates

The following templates have been created according to the TELEMETRY visual identity and clearly show the EU funding information:

- Word Document – Deliverable template

The figure displays two screenshots of a TELEMETRY deliverable template. The left screenshot shows the title page with the following content:

Funded by the European Union | Horizon Europe Project TELEMETRY | HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02

TELEMETRY [101119747]: Trustworthy methodologies, open knowledge & automated tools for security testing of IoT software, hardware & ecosystems

TELEMETRY logo

[DX.X Deliverable Title]

Project Reference No	TELEMETRY - 101119747
Deliverable	DX.X Deliverable Title
Work package	WPX: Title of WP
Type	R - Document, report DEM - Demonstrator, pilot, prototype DEC - Websites, patent filings, videos, etc DATA - datasets, microdata, etc DMP - Data Management Plan OTHER
Dissemination Level	PU - Public (fully open) SEN - Sensitive (limited under the conditions of the Grant Agreement) R-UE/EU-R - EU Classified (RESTREINT-UE/EU-RESTRICTED) C-UE/EU-C - EU Classified (CONFIDENTIEL-UE/EU-CONFIDENTIAL) S-UE/EU-S - EU Classified (SECRET-UE/EU-SECRET)
Date	DD/MM/YYYY
Status	Draft vx.x, Final vx.x
Editor(s)	
Contributor(s)	
Reviewer(s)	
Document description	

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The right screenshot shows the following content:

Funded by the European Union | TELEMETRY - 101119747 | HORIZON-CL3-2022-CS-01-02 | TELEMETRY logo

Disclaimer
The TELEMETRY project is funded by the European Union under grant agreement ID 101119747. The information and views set out in this website are those of the TELEMETRY Consortium only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the European Research Executive Agency (REA). Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

Document Revision History

Version	Date	Modifications Introduced	
		Modification Reason	Modified by

28-02-24 | [DX.X - Deliverable title] | Page | 2

Figure 6: TELEMETRY deliverable template (screenshots)

- A PowerPoint – Presentation Template

Figure 7: TELEMTRY presentation template (screenshots)

All consortium partners will adopt the templates provided to maintain visual coherency throughout the project.

More templates for internal materials of the project (Agenda, Minutes, Peer Review Report etc.) have been also created following the guidelines of the logo design and have been presented in deliverable “D6.1- Project Management Handbook and Quality Assurance Plan”.

5.6 Visuals

Several visuals have been prepared to present the project on social media using the TELEMETRY visual identity. The project logo will be present in every visual to maintain coherency throughout all communication efforts.

6 Dissemination & Communication Time-plan

As shown in previous chapters of this document, the dissemination and communication strategy of TELEMETRY is based on three phases:

- Phase I: Inform & Connect
- Phase II: Demonstrate & Contribute
- Phase III: Share & Convince

Within these three phases, there are different aspects to address. Figure 8 is a short overview of important deadlines and actions that will play a big role in the dissemination and communication of TELEMETRY.

Figure 8: Dissemination and Communication Time plan

Table 11 below outlines the plans for key activities foreseen at the first year of the project.

Table 11: Dissemination and Communication Time plan for Year 1

Delivery Date	Activity	Remark	Status	Lead/Contributors
M3	Project website	Creation and maintenance	Planned	ATC
M3	Social media (1-X, 2-LinkedIn)	Creation and maintenance	1- Delivered 2- Planned	ATC
M6	Press Release	Compilation of First Issue	Planned	ATC
M6	Dissemination and Communication Plan (D5.1)	Compilation and submission	Delivered	ATC with contribution from partners
M8	Flyer	Creation	Planned	ATC with contribution from partners

M9	Newsletter	Creation of First Issue	Planned	ATC with contribution from partners
M18	Report on Dissemination and Communication Activities (interim version)	Compilation	Planned	ATC with contribution from partners

7 Monitoring and Evaluation

7.1 Quantitative & Qualitative Evaluation of TELEMETRY Dissemination and Communication

In accordance with the evaluation criteria and indicators for measurement of the level of success of dissemination and communication activities, the qualitative and quantitative aspects of evaluation will be examined in detail in the following paragraphs.

In order to capture the effectiveness of dissemination and communication, a combination of criteria or feedback mechanisms is being used to measure the effectiveness of each dissemination and communication activity. The project has developed an online monitoring template, which all partners are using to register and monitor their activities. Information to be contained in this template is as following:

For Publications:

Type of PID1 (repository)	Choose from the list: DOI, Handle, ARK, URI, Purl, Other, None
PID (publisher version of record)	Insert PID reference (PID -Publisher version of record is the one assigned to the publication by the publisher)
PID of deposited publication	Insert PID reference (PID of deposited publication is the PID that the published manuscript or the final peer-reviewed version takes when deposited to the open repository)
Type of publication	Choose from the list: Article in Journal, Publication in conference proceeding/workshop, Books/monographs, Chapters in books, Thesis/dissertation, Other
Link to publication	The link should be added only if PID/DOI is not available
Title of the scientific publication	Insert title of the publication. If it is a book chapter please add the title of the chapter, not the title of the book
Authors	Insert author names. The name of the authors should be complete only if PID/DOI is not available
Title of the journal or equivalent	Insert the title of the journal (in case of a book, please look below)
Number	Insert the number of journal

¹ PID: persistent identifier

ISSN or eISSN	Insert ISSN/ eSSN number. If book insert ISBN.
Publisher	Insert name of the publisher
Month of publication	Insert month of publication
Year of publication	Insert year of publication
Was the publication available in open access through the repository at the time of publication	Choose from the list: Yes, No
Peer-reviewed	Choose from the list: Yes, No
PID of Book	Insert PID reference if book chapter
Book title	Insert book title if book chapter
Did you charge OA publishing fees to the project?	Choose from the list: Yes, No
Type of publishing venue	Choose from the list: Hybrid venue, Full open access venue, Full subscription venue (only if OA publishing fees are charged to the project) <i>Note: APCs/BPCs paid to hybrid publishing venues are non-eligible costs under Horizon Europe</i>
Article processing costs that will be charged to the project	Type the amount in (€)

For Dissemination Activities:

Partner Organisation	Choose from the list: NSN, SINTEF, MTU, I4RI, ATC, KU Leuven, TIM, ENG, WRCVE, ANTONOV ASTC, UoS
Responsible Person	Fill in the cell with the name(s) of the person(s) who will be responsible for gathering input for the dissemination activity.
Other partners involved	Indicate one or more partners: NSN, SINTEF, MTU, I4RI, ATC, KU Leuven, TIM, ENG, WRCVE, ANTONOV ASTC, UoS
Dissemination activity name	Insert communication name
Description	Insert description of implemented communication activity
Target audience	Choose from the list: Citizens, Civil society, EU Institutions, Industry, business partners, Innovators, International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.), Investors, Local authorities, National authorities, Regional authorities, Research communities, Specific user communities (if applicable)
Communication channel	Choose from the list: Event (including conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.), Exhibition, Interview, Media article, Newsletter, Press release, Printed materials (including brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.), Social media, TV/Radio, Campaign, Video, Website, Other
Outcome	Insert key performance indicators
Status	Choose from the list: Cancelled, Delivered, Ongoing, Postponed

For Communication Activities:

Partner Organisation	Choose from the list: NSN, SINTEF, MTU, I4RI, ATC, KU Leuven, TIM, ENG, WRCVE, ANTONOV ASTC, UoS
Responsible Person	Fill in the cell with the name(s) of the person(s) who will be responsible for gathering input for the communication activity.
Other partners involved	Indicate one or more partners: NSN, SINTEF, MTU, I4RI, ATC, KU Leuven, TIM, ENG, WRCVE, ANTONOV ASTC, UoS
Communication activity name	Insert communication name

Description	Insert description of implemented communication activity
Target audience	Choose from the list: Citizens, Civil society, EU Institutions, Industry, business partners, Innovators, International organisation (UN body, OECD, etc.), Investors, Local authorities, National authorities, Regional authorities, Research communities, Specific user communities (if applicable)
Communication channel	Choose from the list: Event (including conference, meeting, workshop, internet debate, round table, group discussion, etc.), Exhibition, Interview, Media article, Newsletter, Press release, Printed materials (including brochure, leaflet, posters, stickers, banners, etc.), Social media, TV/Radio, Campaign, Video, Website, Other
Outcome	Insert key performance indicators
Status	Choose from the list: Cancelled, Delivered, Ongoing, Postponed

For every blog post on TELEMETRY website, the needed information to be filled in is as follows:

Title	Title of the blog post
Description	The main text of the blog post
Resources	Indication of (links to) presentations, photographs, or other relative material

For measuring effectiveness of the online communication, the following metrics must be compiled on a monthly basis, by the responsible partner:

Website	Google or Matomo analytics will be integrated into the web page to collect generic analytics information such as users-visitors, sessions, average session duration, page views, new visitors, and returning visitors.
Social media	Number of followers, number of tweets/posts, impressions/reach, link clicks

Table 12 below presents a list of target values for quantitative indicators based on which the dissemination and communication impact of the project will be evaluated.

Table 12: TELEMETRY Dissemination and Communication quantitative indicators

Project website	1000+ web page visits per year; 200+ material downloads per year
Collaboration with relevant EU projects	>4. At least 1 meeting per year & 1 joint activity.
Liaison with relevant EU communities	Representation and active participation of TELEMETRY on 4+ working groups by project end.
Scientific publications and presentations at conferences, seminars, workshops, etc.	20+ journal papers and conference papers accepted over the duration of TELEMETRY; participation in 15+ events.
Articles in printed/online media	20+ journal papers and conference papers accepted over the duration of TELEMETRY
Press releases	5+ press releases
Videos	2+ promotional project videos
Brochures	1500+ Brochure (flyers) distribution

7.2 Expected Impact

The outcomes of TELEMETRY dissemination and communication activities should ensure a positive impact in the domain of cyber security and IoT. Moreover, TELEMETRY is expected to be extremely beneficial for various target groups that are defined, not only by their direct interest in the project results as potential users (for example Component Developers (CDs), System Integrators (SIs) and System Operators (SOs) but also by their institutional and scientific status (i.e. universities and scientific community).

The impact of dissemination and communication will be analyzed based on several aspects that need to be taken into account such as:

Inputs	The resources to be used for reaching the objectives
Activities	The dissemination and communication activities to be performed
Outputs	The direct results of activities - a set of quantitative and qualitative indicators to measure outputs
Outcomes	Longer-term effects on the people, communities, or domains
Impact	The impact may be estimated after a deeper investigation and longer-term assessment, and based on the evaluation of all previous components

7.3 Impact in Relation to Objectives

Table 13 below summarizes the original dissemination & communication objectives and how the project aims to deliver impact.

Table 13: Impact in relation to dissemination and communication objectives

Original Dissemination & Communication Objectives	How TELEMETRY Delivers Impact
Provide visibility and public awareness of the project by following a strategy targeting the critical actors in the broader European community and national public bodies	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Composition of a project identity kit that is appealing to target audiences; • Uses online channels to reach experts and non-experts alike; • Publication of communication material (flyers, newsletters, press releases, video etc.)
Publish results in international industrial and academic conferences, workshops, and journals, to inform the relevant interested third parties (academic/research and private/public organisations) about TELEMETRY	Publications (in journals and conferences), participation to relative events (conferences, workshops, etc.)
Support cluster collaboration	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Identifies EU Initiatives and national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms for collaboration • Clustering activities to exploit synergies between other projects financed under the same topic and increase their impact. Common areas of collaboration will be agreed, similar technology needs will be identified, and common

	dissemination channels and activities will be scheduled.
Promote community engagement and provide stakeholders' training for knowledge transfer	Organization of workshops and demonstrations

7.4 Risks & Issues related to Dissemination and Communication

The main risks related to the dissemination and communication side of the project are presented in Table 14 below. These risks, as well as any other identified risk or potential issue related to dissemination and communication, will be monitored and mitigated by the Project Coordinator. However, the WP5 Leader will also examine these risks on a regular basis and report any changes to the Project Coordinator.

Table 14: Risks related to Dissemination and Communication

Risk Statement	Level of Impact	Mitigating measures
Reluctance from partners to conduct dissemination and communication actions	Low	Clearly defined communication and dissemination roles and trajectories of partners (Academics focus on Academic publications, Technical focus on Business related communication and dissemination actions).
Communication and Dissemination actions fail to meet the relevant KPIs.	Medium	Partners will follow the Dissemination and Communication strategy and plan of TELEMTRY. The PC in coordination with the WP leader (ATC) will monitor the evolution (and performance) of dissemination and communication actions and propose additional targeted activities.

8 Partners' Roles & Responsibilities

NOKIA will disseminate the results and outcomes of TELEMETRY to its Business Units to re-use them in its products, solutions, and services offerings. Following the trend to open and distributed networks in the telecommunication area, since secure and privacy respecting networks are becoming more and more important for future network topologies. NOKIA will also disseminate towards the scientific community, through papers for conferences.

SINTEF will participate actively in the writing and presentation of academic papers documenting project results, targeting conferences, workshops, and journals from recognized publishers with rigorous peer-review policies. SINTEF will leverage agreements with major publishers that allow immediate availability of SHERPA ROMEO Green content, without embargo period. SINTEF will also participate in dissemination events targeted at practitioners and end-users.

MTU will disseminate scientific results through publications in relevant workshops, conferences and journals. Further, MTU will engage with relevant stakeholders in its network and will leverage the outcomes of the project through the development and delivery of research informed education and training programs as part of MTU's CyberSkills initiative.

i4RI will disseminate TELEMETRY's results through the different channels that it possesses. This would be the usage of social networks, as well as through blogs and publications in relevant workshops and dissemination events. Besides these, i4RI will engage with researchers and contacts from the industrial domain, especially under the AI realm, and through the fora i4RI has access to and is in contact.

ATC is leading Task 5.1 "Dissemination, Communications & Outreach" of WP5: "Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach" and will oversee the planning, execution, monitoring, and reporting of project dissemination and communication activities. ATC will be responsible for the definition of the overall dissemination and communication strategy, with the support from the rest of the consortium. Moreover, ATC is responsible for the creation and maintenance of the various online channels (project website and social media) that will be used to communicate the project results, as well as for the production of the project identity kit and content to support the communication of the TELEMETRY project. Additionally, ATC will actively communicate project objectives and results through its network of partners and established distribution channels towards its customer base as well as multiply the visibility of the project's activities and results via each own online channel (website, social media).

KUL would design and conduct implementations on cryptographic protocol tailored for the software patches, and then disseminate their results and publish them, in the form of academic research papers, into various conferences, workshops and journals in their relevant areas of discipline. Furthermore, KUL would also publicise their work via internal social media outlets, blog posts and research seminars.

TIM intends to leverage the outcomes of TELEMETRY by disseminating them by means of articles, blogs and security events. This initiative seeks to bolster existing methodologies, tools, and expertise utilized in assessing and certifying network and security devices before their integration into Telecom Italia's operational environments. The insights gained will also contribute to augmenting the internal security awareness initiatives and training programs for

the security personnel. Additionally, collaboration with entities such as the European SDO and other relevant groups will ensure alignment with industry standards and regulatory frameworks, further enhancing the effectiveness of security measures.

ENG dissemination activities will include conferences (both cross-sectoral and focused on use cases' domains), workshops, relevant exhibitions, scientific ENG will inform and engage all the relevant stakeholders in its network as well as many end-users as possible, making them ready and able to use the knowledge and results produced throughout project. Dissemination targets can be divided in: (a) Research/collaboration level, including the Cybersec4Europe competence centre, the European Cyber Security Organisation, the Alliance for Internet of Things Innovation, the FIWARE ecosystem, the Big Data Value Association, the AI4EU observatory, etc.; (b) market level, including publications, non-scientific publications (including company newsletters, social media posts and press releases).

WRCVE will disseminate the results of its project activities to the wider research and industrial community. WRCVE plans to publish the achievements in international scientific and technical publications and present them at international scientific conferences and seminars.

ANTONOV ASTC will communicate and disseminate TELEMETRY developments and outcomes via its social media network to collaborators, partners, constructors in the domain of aerospace.

UoS has the objective of publishing and disseminating its activities in TELEMETRY in conferences and journals and has a preference towards collaborative publication and dissemination efforts where it co-authors publications with other TELEMETRY partners, and actively seeks collaboration with outside partners.

9 Conclusions

This deliverable is part of the TELEMETRY project's WP5: "Dissemination, Exploitation and Outreach" and provides information regarding the dissemination and communication strategy as well as the plan to raise awareness, share knowledge, attract potential stakeholders. This document presents an overview of the targeted audiences and identifies the channels, tools, and activities to be used to disseminate and communicate the project's results.

Moreover, relevant dissemination events and scientific journals that are found suitable for presenting the project and promoting its goals have been identified. In addition, EU Initiatives and national or regional initiatives, funding programs and platforms that synergies are envisioned as well as other EU projects for collaboration are listed. All these aspects are important and essential for the impact of project results and to ensure that the whole consortium will try to maximize its efforts to make third parties aware of the project outcomes. The proposed dissemination and communication activities will be continuously monitored and accordingly updated, so this deliverable provided an overview of what is known and planned at the time of writing this document.